

Designing curriculum to acknowledge quantitative, sociocultural, critical, and spatial ways of knowing in mathematics teacher education

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The novel framework described in this manuscript was designed by the researchers to make explicit the intersection of socio-cultural, critical, quantitative, and spatial ways of knowing the world, which are inherent in mathematics education and quantitative learning environments more broadly. This work builds on the Teaching Mathematics for Spatial Justice (TMSpJ) framework of Rubel, Hall-Wieckert, and Lim to consider how TMSpJ can be incorporated into mathematics teacher education, with particular attention given to interrogating the spatial realities constructed by the educational system in rural areas. We suggest that our framework can be a powerful guide for designing learning experiences for pre-service mathematics teachers (PST). As part of this proceeding, we will first define the framework and then share a statistics unit for PST that incorporates the critical aspects of knowing the world.

Introduction

The social and historical dimensions of reality have long been important when considering the teaching and learning of mathematics in a social context (Lerman, 2000), and more recently political dimensions have been highlighted in the sociopolitical (Gutiérrez, 2013). However, a dimension that has been somewhat neglected is that of the spatial aspect. In the introduction of Edward Soja's (2010) book *Seeking Social Justice*, he describes social (in)justice as "an integral and formative component of justice itself, a vital part of how justice and injustice are socially constructed and evolve over time" (p. 1). Spatial justice, for the purpose of our research, considers individual experiences defined by space, and how circumstances are determined by geographies that are socially constructed. Larnell and Bullock (2018) created a socio-spatial framework for urban mathematics education claiming a spatial turn in mathematics education. A recent push in that direction has been spearheaded by Rubel and her team in their work on conceptualizing *Teaching Mathematics for Spatial Justice* (TMSpJ; Rubel, Hall-Wieckert, & Lim, 2017, 2016; Rubel, Lim, Hall-Wieckert, & Sullivan, 2016). In their work, they developed and implemented lessons involving spatial justice themes that intersected with critical pedagogy. Their work was situated in a mathematics course for social justice in high school and undergraduate classes serving

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predominantly underserved students in New York City (Rubel et al., 2016). This work shows the potential that considering spatial justice in mathematics education can provide tools and design heuristics that encourage more socially focused opportunities in mathematics classrooms.

Drawing from the seminal work of Rubel and company (Rubel et al., 2017; Rubel et al., 2016; Rubel et al., 2016), our work incorporates the notion of spatial justice in two fundamentally different ways. One way is by developing an epistemological framework for the teaching and learning of mathematics that explicitly acknowledges sociocultural, critical, quantitative, and spatial ways of knowing the world drawing from Soja's work (2010). The second way is by investigating how such an epistemological framework could be used in designing curriculum for pre-service mathematics teachers, whereas the activity would also provide a critical lens for the pre-service teachers to make sense of their future classroom environments.

We assert that spatial ways of knowing are particularly relevant and important to consider in pre-service teacher education because education systems themselves are based on geopolitical boundaries. We used a design approach (Cobb et al., 2003) to focus on pragmatic problems in learning ecologies, specifically how to incorporate spatial justice meaningfully into the preparation of mathematics teachers. As design work is iterative, through the process of delving into the literature and applying our theories in practice we refined our problem into the following specific research question we consider in this paper. *How can the design of learning experiences for PSTs be framed to create opportunities for PSTs to interrogate systems that they are a part of using practices from quantitative, critical, socio-cultural, and spatial ways of knowing the world?*

Teaching mathematics for spatial justice

TMSpJ was developed by considering place-based education in conjunction with Critical Mathematics Education to create a way of thinking about teaching mathematics that drew upon spatial perspectives in relation to reading and writing the world (Rubel et al., 2016). To that end, we began by considering how to incorporate Rubel, Hall-Wieckert, and Lim's (2016) design heuristics in our teacher education program. The guiding questions they used to initially designing their work include:

- How does the system work?
- What is the system's geography?
- Who participates, where, and how often?
- How is the system experienced in peoples' everyday lives?
- Is the system fair? How could it be transformed to be fairer? (Rubel et al., 2016, p. 564)

The obstacle, when considering our work, was in thinking of how to communicate the design heuristics we were using to PSTs who had little to no prior experiences with the practices of critical literacy or interrogating systems. The design heuristics developed by Rubel, Hall-Wieckert, and Lim (2016) was explicitly situated in a critical lens drawing upon

Designing curriculum to acknowledge quantitative, sociocultural, critical, and spatial ways the work of critical scholars (Freire, 1970; Freire & Macedo, 1987; Gutstein, 2003, 2006). However, the nuances of the ontological and epistemological stances inherent in working within a critical lens are not made explicit in the guiding questions, so that someone lacking familiarity with the perspective may struggle when engaging in the work. In considering Soja’s (2010) work we zoomed out to consider the ontological perspective he discusses and then zoomed in to an epistemological perspective to consider the design of curriculum for PSTs incorporating spatial justice.

Ways of knowing framework

The epistemological ways of knowing our world are constituted by socially, historically, and spatially situated discourses. In striving to define an epistemological perspective and considering socio-cultural theories of learning (Boaler & Greeno, 2000; Lave & Wenger, 1991; Lerman, 2000) in mathematics education, we began to realize that in our design process we were struggling to identify what specifically the practices were for someone to investigate a system where all four ways of knowing are incorporated that are the focus of our work.

Our framework is based on the notion that there are many different ways of knowing or coming to know the world. Some ways of knowing are privileged in society and by institutions, whereas others are often marginalized, silenced, or discredited. We acknowledge that our framework is not comprehensive of all the ways of knowing the world, instead, we focus explicitly on four important ways of knowing (socio-cultural, critical, quantitative, and spatial) in quantitative learning environments that have been considered and investigated in various combinations by scholars in the past (d’Ambrosio, 1985; Frankenstein, 2009; Gutstein, 2006; Lerman, 2000; Rubel et al., 2016; Skovsmose, 1994).

Ways of Knowing	Quantitative	Socio-cultural	Critical	Spatial
Key Practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Measurement – Collecting data – Modeling the world through quantification – Shaping the world through quantification – Problem-solving through quantification and abstraction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Using funds of knowledge of communities to make sense of the world – Considering the ways different communities of practice come to know the world – Drawing upon the assets of a community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Reading and writing the world – Making sense of social structures – Transforming social structures – Problematizing structural causes of (in)justice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Considering how space/social structures shape/are shaped by one another – Understanding that spatial/social structures are historical – Interrogating the political space, one is situated in – Reflecting on and transforming the physical space one is situated in

Table 1: Ways of Knowing Framework

When establishing our Ways of Knowing (WoK) Framework we felt as if all four aspects were essential to create a comprehensive understanding of issues related to social inequities. The strength of our framework is that the interconnectedness between the ways of knowing is central and provides a lens that allows social constructs to be fully examined.

Guiding objectives for designing curriculum for teacher education

In working to design curriculum, our specific audience was pre-service elementary teachers (E-PSTs) in a content and methods class. To engage in all four aspects of the WoK Framework we described, we began our design work by considering learning objectives for each way of knowing for the unit we would design for E-PSTs.

In the sections that follow, we discuss how we developed the learning objectives for a unit by consulting past research and our work to provide a descriptive example of the process of building curriculum from the WoK framework for others. We also provide an illustrative example of an activity that highlights how we designed the curriculum to incorporate all the aspects of the framework to interrogate aspects of the education system.

Quantitative

For the unit we designed, we focused specifically on statistics content and practices. There are some crucial differences between mathematics and statistics that make it particularly powerful for interrogating the world. One of those elements is that context is central to the discipline of statistics (Cobb & Moore, 1997; Wild & Pfannkuch, 1999) and the statistical inquiry process that is at the heart of what is recommended for statistics instruction in K-12 education. Another difference between mathematics and statistics is the focus on variability. There must be variability in data to use statistics, statistical questions are those that anticipate variability, and variability is one of the main aspects of a distribution we try to measure to describe it and to do inferential statistics. The Guidelines for Assessment and Instruction in Statistical Education (GAISE) framework recommends beginning with a focus on variability within a group before considering variability between groups and co-variability (Franklin et al., 2007). Building off the GAISE framework the Statistical Education of Teachers (SET) document further discusses the statistical preparation of teacher including specific recommendations by grade level (Franklin et al., 2015). Because the focus of our work is on elementary teachers it made sense to work from the SET recommendations to determine the learning objectives for the quantitative ways of knowing aspect of the framework, which focus on the content, pedagogical content and horizon knowledge for teaching statistics in elementary grade levels (grades 1-5). Based on these goals the design of our instructional unit focused predominantly on content knowledge. In the content course, only four weeks can be dedicated to the topic of statistics, and for the methods course, the statistics content is predominantly in one unit.

Spatial

For considering the spatial components of our unit we drew from past work of Rubel, Hall-Wieckert, Lim (2017). In their work with high school and community college students, they looked at how to bring issues of spatial justice into the mathematics classroom. Though our

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population is pre-service teachers they are also undergraduates and are mostly of similar age as the students in Rubel, Hall-Wieckert, and Lim’s work, therefore we believe the practices translate well. In developing a set of analytic codes to investigate how the students in their study engaged with the spatial tools they provided they creating a coding scheme that was a mix of a map-reading framework from Morris (2013) and a statistical graph literacy framework from Shaughnessy (2007). Soja (2010) in his work described three different levels of spatial understanding, macro, meso, and micro geographical elements. Macro looks at the political aspects of space, meso, how processes evolve in a spatial context and the uneven development of space, and micro focuses on the inequalities created through decisions made at an institutional level. For our planned activities, we focused on the meso-geographical level and how that impacted the student’s educational experience.

Designed curriculum for teacher education

With the creation of the TMSpJ curriculum, using the WoK Framework we had five focused goals for the students.

- Use descriptive statistics and graphs to consider schools as an aggregate.
- Use statistical investigations to interrogate claims.
- Create a final project that brought the tenets of this work together.
- Use spatial representations of data to investigate statistical questions.
- Create statistical questions to guide an investigation of educational data.

Quantitative (Statistics)	Spatial
1. Develop the necessary content knowledge and statistical reasoning skills to implement the recommended statistics topics for elementary-grade students	1. Recognize and interpret components of a map
2. Develop the content knowledge associated with the middle school–level statistics content	2. Use maps to compare two places
3. Develop an understanding of how statistical concepts in middle grades build on content developed in elementary-grade levels	3. Identify a pattern in a map related to more than two places toward building a spatial argument
4. Develop an understanding of how statistical content in elementary grades is connected to other subject areas in elementary grades	4. Interpret causes of a spatial pattern
	5. Make connections between the context and the spatial pattern
Critical	Sociocultural
1. Interrogate structural elements of the education system	1. Consider the culture of a class or school
2. Interrogate one’s subjectivity concerning perceptions of education and the education system	2. Consider the cultures of people that are part of the community a school is situated in and serves
	3. Reflect on one’s own culture and subjectivity.

Table 2: Learning objectives for statistics unit situated in the Ways of Knowing Framework.

Designing a unit using the ways of knowing framework

Working from the focused goals we then sought to flesh out the learning activities for the unit. Brief descriptions of each of the major activities in the unit can be found in Table 3. The overarching thought behind our design was to start with students focusing on thinking about themselves, then zooming out to think about their class, then the community surrounding the institution, and finally to the state and possibly beyond. In this way, we were able to start by meeting the student where they were at and then expand into more and more technical statistical ideas while also zooming out in terms of the context under consideration. The context of the educational system was at the core of all the investigations that were designed for the unit to situate the unit in a context of interest and relevance to the students who were PST's.

Identity, Census, and Statistics

This activity has students begin by students responding to the prompt, "Write a short description (4-6 sentences) of how you would describe your identity to someone else," Students are asked to synthesize their descriptions into five words. Students reflect on what is gained and lost by synthesizing their descriptions into words. As a class, all students aggregate their five words and are asked to then organize the words in a way that helps them to respond to the question of what the identity of students in the class is. Once students have completed their organization of the word data they are then asked to write a brief description of their class based on the word data that they then share. Students then reflect on how their descriptions of themselves compared to their class descriptions and on what is gained and lost by moving from their descriptions to descriptions of the class. The activity is connected to the practice of statistics including what counts as data, how data is collected, and that statistics focus on aggregates, which are related to samples, sampling, and making an inference.

Statistical Investigations: Questions and Data

This activity introduces students to the statistical investigation cycle from the GAISE framework (Franklin et al., 2007) and developing their understanding of the question and collecting data elements of the cycle. Students take a survey before class to collect data. During class, students are presented with the main types of variables (categorical: ordinal and nominal; quantitative: discrete and continuous) and provided examples of each. They are then asked to identify the variable types from the survey. Then the different types of questions (research, statistical, and analysis) are discussed and more specific criteria are presented of what makes a good statistical question. Students are then asked to come up with a statistical question they could ask given the data they have from the survey.

Statistical Investigations: Analysis

For this activity, students explore data on the schools (School Report Card) near the institution that the students are attending. The students begin by exploring several categorical variables on the school report cards and considering how those variables are measured, what they tell them about the school, what they don't tell them about the school, how the data can be organized and visualized, and how to ask and answer statistical questions using categorical variables. Students then move on to considering quantitative variables in the context of school report card data and the main ideas considered on categorical variables.

Statistical Investigations: Interpretation and Interrogation

Students are provided a statistical argument presented by the superintendent of the state educational authority. They were asked to consider the questions: “What do you notice? What are you left wondering? What message is the person who created the infographic trying to convey?” The argument gets at the difference between how the mean and median measure the center of a distribution and how outliers impact them in the context of income data. To help highlight the issue, students then look at a dataset from the American Communities survey that is a representative sample of the region around the institution and investigate the question of what the typical income of people in the region is. Students use the analysis techniques they learned in the previous activity to then respond to the question and connect what they learn back to the data argument they were considering earlier and interrogate the argument. Students are then shown two different types of spatial data analysis tools one from the state educational authority (<https://gdacreporting.ondemand.sas.com/srcfinance>) and one from the Opportunity Atlas (<https://www.opportunityatlas.org>). Opportunity Atlas allows individuals to view the micro-level of a community, metrics that the program affords are measures such as income, commuting zone, and job growth. The program allows you to input a zip code within the United States and through various representations consider the make-up of unique regions. Students are then asked to use the tools to consider the following question about the context of income: “What trends do you see in the average teacher pay based on location? Are those trends mirrored in the opportunity data? Explain.” Students then present their explorations.

Considering Space

To learn about spatial ways of knowing more specifically students are presented with descriptions of what spatial means, spatial relationships to consider, and what spatial justice is. Students are then given three different mapping tools to investigate the region around the institution in relation to the schools they were investigating with the school report card data from earlier. One map shows the school district boundaries. Another map shows the actual location of the school buildings. The final map allows students to investigate various “opportunity” variables. Students were asked to consider what the maps helped tell them about the schools and what information they don’t tell them.

Comparing Distributions

Building on students’ understanding of statistical investigations and applying their knowledge, they construct an investigation comparing two or more groups on a quantitative variable. Students learn how to compare distribution, which measures to focus on, and how to interpret findings. To continue to build the students’ understanding, both quantitative and critical, we chose to use the Common Online Data Analysis Platform (CODAP) software, with a constructed data set related to the target area. CODAP allows individuals to work from a set of data, choosing specific variables, creating different visual representations with ease. CODAP allows an individual to drag and drop self-selected variables. The reason we chose to include a program to construct the representation, was that our focus for meeting the needs of the WoK was on the analysis of graphs, not the construction of the graph.

 Putting it all Together: Statistical Investigation Project

This activity is a culminating project meant to pull together all the ideas that were focused on in the unit and provide the student an opportunity to show what they have learned. For the project, students are given a data set that contains information from the school report cards they were considering earlier but this time for all the schools in the state. Students are asked to come up with a statistical question that requires them to compare two distributions and then do a statistical investigation to respond to the question. They are then asked to delve deeper by investigating some pattern or outcome they observed in their statistical investigation using spatial data tools and other data sources they explored during the unit.

For the final culminating activity our overarching goals included:

- Quantitative: Focus on graphing and descriptive statistics, describing univariate categorical and quantitative variables, informally compare categorical and quantitative variables between groups.
- Socio-cultural: school culture, student backgrounds, student lived experiences.
- Critical: structural issues in access to education
- Spatial: location of educational opportunities, spatial distribution of opportunities, goods, and people, spatial boundaries of educational systems and policies.

Students then created 15-minute screen capture videos presenting their investigations and deeper dives into the context.

Table 3: Descriptions of main designed activities for statistics unit

Conclusion

Through our work, we realize that this work is first and foremost necessary, but not simple. Our students, when engaging in activities supported and defined by our framework were able to consider situations through a lens that may have been novel to them. In focusing on specific aspects of the framework and then bringing it all together in the Statistical Investigation Project, we allowed the students to consider the quantitative, spatial, critical, and socio-cultural space in which they reside with diligent consideration. Through our Ways of Knowing Framework, in tandem with the tenets of Teaching Mathematics for Spatial Justice, we strived to promote a mindset that encourages individual growth that we hope is lifelong. Our goal throughout this research project has been to broaden the understanding of all individuals that together create a community, namely in rural settings. Based on our research we advocate that the use of our framework can be a powerful guide for designing learning experiences for pre-service mathematics teachers (PST).

Education and access to opportunities often determine trajectories established for students, especially in mathematics. In using the proposed framework to work with pre-service teachers, we have seen our students begin to gain insight into multiple ways of knowing that we hope will help them to better understand and support their future students. We hypothesize through such experiences the lens through which they see and understand the world becomes inclusive, allowing their ways of knowing to look at the social, critical, and spatial challenges. When considering how the uneven development of geography

Designing curriculum to acknowledge quantitative, sociocultural, critical, and spatial ways impacts the opportunities of students in various communities, it is essential to equip pre-service teachers to critically examine and validate those practices that fail to provide equal opportunity.

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